

Radiological Analysis of Component Orientation in Un-Cemented Total Hip Arthroplasty via Posterolateral ApproachDevpriya Jaiswal¹, Mahesh Kulkarni², Sandeep Vijayan³, Sharath Kumar Rao⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna, Bihar.²Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Kasturba Medical College, Manipal.³Additional Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Kasturba Medical College, Manipal⁴Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Kasturba Medical College, Manipal

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Abstract:

Introduction: Total Hip Arthroplasty (THA) is a common surgical intervention for patients with symptomatic osteoarthritis, aimed at alleviating pain and improving mobility. Accurate positioning of the acetabular cup and femoral stem is critical for the longevity and function of the implant. This study focuses on the radiological evaluation of acetabular and femoral component orientation in uncemented THA performed using the posterolateral approach.

Objective: The primary objective of this study is to assess the accuracy of acetabular cup inclination and anteversion, along with femoral stem alignment, using radiological analysis, and to correlate these measurements with patient outcomes.

Materials and Methods: This observational analytical study included 52 patients who underwent uncemented THA between January 2016 and October 2022. All surgeries were performed using the posterolateral approach. Radiographic evaluation was conducted to measure acetabular cup inclination, anteversion, and femoral stem alignment. Postoperative radiographs were analysed for each patient, and angles were calculated using specific radiological markers.

Results: The average acetabular cup inclination was found to be within the safe range of 40°-45° in 82% of patients, while anteversion was between 15°-25° in 75% of cases. Femoral stem alignment was within 5° of neutral in 90% of patients. Mispositioning of components was associated with a higher incidence of complications such as dislocation and limb length discrepancy.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of precise radiological evaluation in ensuring optimal implant positioning in THA. The majority of patients showed satisfactory alignment of both the acetabular cup and femoral stem, correlating with improved clinical outcomes. However, deviations from the ideal alignment can lead to postoperative complications, underscoring the need for careful intraoperative techniques and postoperative assessment.

Keywords: Total Hip Arthroplasty, Acetabular Cup Orientation, Femoral Stem Alignment, Radiological Evaluation, Posterolateral Approach, Uncemented THA.

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Introduction

One of the biggest joints in the human body is the hip joint. The joint is of the ball-and-socket kind. The socket is formed by the acetabulum, a large part of the pelvic bone. The ball is a representation of the femoral head or top end of the femur.

Its functionality depends on the hip joint capsule. It creates a seal over the joint area, offers passive stability by restricting motion, and actively stabilises the joint by forming articular surfaces and proprioceptive nerve endings. Femoral head prosthesis, like the one created in 1948 in France by Jean and Robert Judet, was the first joint replacement used in clinical practice after several

studies in the first half of the 20th century. Sir John Charnley of the UK made a significant advance in THA in 1962 when he introduced metal or plastic bearings]. Every year, more than one million THA procedures are performed worldwide, and this figure is expected to double within the next two decades. More than 90% of patients have symptomatic osteoarthritis, which means they have persistent pain and disability.

The prevalence is rising due to an ageing population and the obesity epidemic. [2] For patients with hip osteoarthritis (OA), THA is a successful and affordable operation that helps them

restore pain-free mobility by replacing damaged bone and cartilage with prosthetic components [3, 4 (Figure 1). Accurate and dependable radiological measurements are thus critical. Plain radiographs

are used in clinical practice for pre-operative planning and postoperative assessment of the THA. In this regard, computed tomography (CT) is the gold standard [5], 6, 7].

Figure 1: Diagram of the prosthetic hip in relation to the hip joint

Aim and Objectives

Aim: To radiologically analyse the acetabular cup and femoral stem orientation in un-cemented total hip arthroplasty performed via the posterolateral approach since January 2016

Objectives: To analyze on standardized postoperative radiographs

- A. Acetabular cup inclination and ante-version
- B. Femoral stem: Varus- Neutral-Valgus alignment Vertical and lateral offset
- C. Limb length discrepancy

Material and Methods

Study Characteristics

- A. Study Design: Observational Analytical Study.
- B. Sample: 52
- C. Study Period: January 2016 to October 2022
- D. An observational analytical study was performed to analyse the component orientation of uncemented total hip replacement performed via posterolateral approach using radiographs between January 2016 and October 2022. Those who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were recruited into the study.

Inclusion Criteria: All primary un-cemented total hip arthroplasty done via the posterolateral approach

Exclusion Criteria

- A. Revision total hip arthroplasty cases
- B. Arthritis due to Developmental dysplasia of hip
- C. Arthritis secondary to acetabular fractures
- D. Patients with Neuro-paralytic disorders

- E. Patients with non-standard post-operative radiographs

Statistical Methods

This study was conducted after official approval from institutional ethical committee (IEC No. 677/2021). The radiological orientation of femoral and acetabular components of uncemented total hip replacement were recorded in the study. Data was then entered on google forms and master chart was made. Statistical analysis of the data was done using the master chart with SPSS version 23. The data collected was represented in the frequencies and percentages. The results of collected data was represented in graphs and pie charts.

Methodology used to evaluate the post-operative radiographs: Immediate post-operative radiographs were analysed which were taken on post-operative day 1 as the patients were kept under observation in post-operative ICU care on the day of the surgery. The images were retrieved from the Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) as Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) Files.

Selection of Radiographs: The patients' postoperative anteroposterior pelvic radiographs and crossed table lateral hip radiographs were examined. To determine whether the radiographic positioning in anteroposterior pelvic radiographs is appropriate, two characteristics were examined

- A. Quotient of pelvic rotation
- B. Pelvic tilt

Only those X-rays with values in the normal range for these parameters were analyzed while those that did not fulfil these criteria were not included so as to avoid measurement error due to poor positioning

Quotient of pelvic rotation [8]: This measurement is used to assess the horizontal pelvic tilt. The quotient of pelvic rotation is derived by dividing the horizontal diameter of the right side's foramen obturatorium by the diameter of the same on the left side. This index would be 1 in the neutral situation. An index of 1.8 to 0.56 is regarded appropriate

Pelvic tilt [9]

The extent between the Sacro-coccygeal junction and the superior end of the symphysis. Acceptable values for males were 2 to 3 cm and 2 to 6 cm for females.

Crossed table lateral view [10]: We will also review post-op lateral cross-table radiographs.

The patient can be positioned supine on an X-ray table and rotate the affected limb 15 degrees internally to acquire a 45-degree X-ray. Hip and knee flexion of the other leg surpasses 80 degrees.

Figure 2: Positioning of patient for Crossed table lateral view

Radiographic analysis

Acetabular Cup Positioning [11]: Two elements determine the acetabular component's orientation:

- The angle between the Trans ischial line and the cup's rim can help interpret an AP hip radiograph.
- A lateral hip radiograph shows anteversion when a line is drawn across the acetabulum's face and another perpendicular to the patient's horizontal plane.

Figure 3: X Ray depicting measurement of acetabular inclination

Figure 4: X Ray depicting measurement of acetabular anteversion

Femoral stem positioning [10]

Neutral positioning: The ideal AP view of a femoral stem would show its tip in the middle of the shaft, with the stem's neutral alignment with the shaft's longitudinal axis.

Figure 5: X Ray depicting neutral positioning of femur stem

Valgus femoral stem positioning: An example of a valgus position would be a component whose proximal half presses against the lateral endosteum and its distal half against the medial endosteum.

Figure 6: X Ray depicting valgus positioning of femur stem

Varus femoral stem positioning: When the proximal part of the femoral component presses against the medial endosteum and the distal part presses against the lateral endosteum, varus placement has taken place.

Figure 7: X Ray depicting varus positioning of femur stem

Femoral offset: [12]: The femoral offset, or horizontal offset, is the horizontal distance between the femoral head's centre of rotation and a line running along the shaft's central axis. The measurement of the distance between the two lines determines the horizontal offset.

Figure 8: X Ray depicting measurement of femoral offset

Limb Length Discrepancy [10]: The pelvic reference line is formed by joining the acetabular tear drops on both sides transversely. The lesser trochanters are connected transversely and serve as femoral reference line.

Figure 9: X Ray depicting measurement of Limb length discrepancy

Review of literature

Anatomy

Proximal Femur: Articular cartilage covers the top two-thirds of the spherical femur and is 4 mm thick above and 3 mm thick at the midway. The ligamentum teres links to the cartilage-free Fovea Centralis (medial to the femoral head axis). With its broad base, the trapezoidal neck of the femur joins to the shaft and narrow end supports the head. The typical neck diameter is 75% of the femoral head.

Acetabulum: A big cup-shaped socket on the hip bone that forms the joint is called the acetabulum, which means "little vinegar cup" in Latin. The hip's three main bones—ilium, ischium, and pubis—form the acetabulum.

Hip Joint: Because of the femoral head's articulation with the acetabulum, the hip joint is a stable and robust multiaxial "Ball and Socket" synovial joint. The hip joint is designed to be stable in a variety of actions. The hip joint's strength and stability are due to:

- The acetabulum's depth.
- Ligament strength and tension
- The femoral head's length and oblique direction.
- Muscle strength in the surrounding muscles.
- Atmospheric pressure

Joint Capsule: A strong but supple capsule encases the hip joint, with an inner synovial membrane and an outer fibrous layer. Near the acetabulum is where you'll find the capsule. The whole neck is now inside the capsule because of the meeting point of the fibrous tissue at the greater trochanter's root and the intertrochanteric line. Nevertheless, the posterior branches are less numerous and the lowest third is located outside the capsule. It reaches the base of the neck and continues anteriorly, superolaterally, and inferiorly.

The fibres of the fibrous capsule run lengthwise from the pelvis to the femur. Some deeper filaments are round. Due to the posterior weakening of the longitudinal fibres in the neck, the Zona Orbicularis' spherical threads are plainly identifiable. The "Ligaments of the Hip Joint" run from the pelvis to the femur in the capsule's fibrous layer. Extension compresses the capsule and draws the femoral head into the acetabulum, tightening fibres and ligaments. This stabilises the joint, however it can only extend 10–20 degrees from vertical. Three ligaments thicken the capsule's longitudinal fibres and connect to the pelvis.

Iliofemoral Ligament/Y-shaped Ligament of Bigelow: The strongest ligament in the body is the iliofemoral ligament anteriorly and superiorly. The base is attached distally to the intertrochanteric line, and the apex is attached proximally to the acetabular rim and anterior inferior iliac spine. This ligament prevents hip hyperextension when standing.

Pubofemoral Ligament: The pubofemoral ligament can be found both above and below the knee. Along the side and bottom of the joint capsule, a muscular layer connects with it after it comes out of the obturator crest of the pubic bone. This ligament gets tighter when the hip is extended or abducted to keep the joint from moving too far outward. It is connected to the medial part of the iliofemoral ligament.

Ischiofemoral Ligament: The posterior ischiofemoral ligament is weakest of the three. It starts in the acetabular rim ischia. Lower fibres spiral upward and laterally to the back and top of the neck, whereas upper fibres travel horizontally. A nexus with the Iliofemoral ligament is at the top. Instead of relaxing transversely in flexion, the fibres spiral and tighten when the trochanter is dragged higher during extension. This ligament causes the femoral head to move inward, increasing hip stability during extension.

Figure 10: Ligaments of the hip joint

Synovial Membrane: A synovial membrane lines the fibrous capsule's interior. Mirrored onto the femoral neck, it covers bones to articular head cartilage. Femoral neck membrane synovial folds (retinacula) run longitudinally.

Acetabular Labarum: The fibrous and cartilaginous acetabular labarum connects to the boundary. The acetabulum mouth narrows and cavity deepens. The labarum circles the femoral head beyond the equator to stabilise the hip joint. The synovial membrane covers both labarum sides.

Ligamentum Teres: The ligament is fan-shaped and flat, and it inserts a little end into the fovea of the femoral head.

A bifurcated, flattened tip connects to the transverse ligament and the borders of the acetabular notch. The ligamentum teres artery, which is a branch of the medial circumflex or obturator artery, flows downstream and into the femoral head.

Vascular Anatomy: Every issue that can arise during intracapsular fracture healing can also occur

with femoral neck fractures. [11] Because the femoral neck inside the capsule lacks a cambium layer, endosteal union is essential for healing. It does not cause peripheral calluses while healing. Synovial fluid can prevent blood clots from forming without direct contact with the damaged bone, preventing secondary healing. The femoral head has few blood vessels due to a misplaced fracture. Hemarthrosis increases hip pressure, worsening circulation due to tamponade.

Arterial Supply: Numerous studies have been conducted on the vascular supply to the proximal end of the femur. Since Crock's description is based on a three-plane analysis, it seems to be the most appropriate and gives anatomic nomenclature standardisation. Crock categorised the proximal femoral arteries into three types:

1. A circle of arteries outside the capsule positioned at the femoral neck's base.
2. Ascending cervical branches in the above-mentioned circle.
3. Arteries in a round ligament

Figure 11: Arterial Supply of Proximal femur

Venous Outflow

At the trochanteric line, capsular veins drain anteromedially into the obturator vein through the foramen. A diffuse plexus around the neck's base gives rise to the femoral vein, which branches out to the lesser and greater trochanters. Smaller veins from the greater trochanter and back of the neck enter plexuses around the ischial tuberosity and greater sciatic notch. Linea aspera veins drain little.

Hip biomechanics

The hip joint acts as a fulcrum by balancing weight and hip abductors [12]. These competing forces combine to maintain a lever pelvis during gait. Hip abductors create a force greater than body weight (B) because a shorter lever arm connects them to the femoral head (A in figure 12). Increased femoral offset lengthens the abductor muscles' lever arm, reducing their work to maintain a regular stride. Reduced hip joint reactive force reduces polyethylene wear. Lateralising the femoral shaft with the hip centre reduces soft tissue tensioning and femoropelvic impingement [13]. An LLD

biomechanical difference of 20 mm: Leg Length Differences effect hip joint strain differently on

shorter sides. Stress may produce long-term problems [14].

Figure 12: Illustration showing how the hip joint balances the forces produced by the hip abductors with the force of the body's weight

Radiological measurements in THA

Leg length discrepancy (LLD): LLD is frequently measured clinically and radiologically before and after THA. A measuring tape can be used to perform the clinical measurement while the patient is supine. The real squaring the pelvis shows long lumbar disc (LLD) between the medial malleolus and the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS) and apparent LLD between the ASIS and the umbilicus [15]. Lumbar spine deviation and pelvic obliquity can affect the latter, indicating an inaccurate LLD. For radiographic measurements, an AP pelvic view

is used. Two proximal femur points, such as the middle or lesser trochanter, and two pelvic points are measured side by side. Fixed points include teardrop or U-figure shapes.

A bony ridge running down the acetabular fossa projects end-on into the pelvic x-ray. Another pelvic bone fixed point is the bottom edge of the ischial tuberosities. See Figures 13, 16, 17, 18, and 19. Teardrop points are recommended as measuring markers instead of other pelvic locations because their vertical position is mostly unaffected by pelvic rotation [20].

Figure 13: Teardrop and ischial tuberosity

Results

The orthopaedics department of Kasturba Medical College in Manipal was the site of the research. The 52 patients who underwent uncemented total hip replacement via the posterolateral method had

their radiographs taken to evaluate their hips for a variety of medical conditions. The outcomes are detailed below.

1. Age: Age ranged from 23 to 79 years with mean age being 51 years.

Table 1: Age of patients in the study population

Age(in years)	Number Of Patients	Percentage (%)
< 30	1	1.92
30-40	11	21.15
40-50	11	21.15
50-60	12	23.07
60-70	12	23.07
70-80	3	5.76
>80	0	0

Figure 14: Graph of age of the patients in the study population

2. Sex: Out of 52 patients, 34 were males and 18 were females

Figure 15: Sex distribution among the patients in the study population

3. Side Operated: Out of 52 patients, 31 patients were operated on the right side while 21 patients underwent THA on the left side.

Figure 16: Side operated in the study population

4. **Preoperative Diagnosis:** Out of 52 patients, 26 were diagnosed to have osteoarthritis, 12 were found to have Avascular necrosis, 4 had fracture of neck of femur. Others were diagnosed with psoriatic arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, IT fracture with non-union and fibrous ankylosis.

Figure 17: Pre-operative diagnosis in the study population

4. **Brand of Prosthesis:** In 52 total hip replacements, 33 Evolutes, 12 DePuy and 1 Meril prosthesis were used while records were not available for 6 cases.
5.

Figure 18: Brand of Prosthesis used in the study population

6. Radiographic Results

Acetabular Inclination: Out of 52 cases, 48(92.3%) patients had an acetabular inclination between 35-55 degrees, 3 patients (5.7%) had an inclination above 55 degrees and 1 patient (1.9%) had an inclination below 35 degrees.

Figure 19: Acetabular Inclination observed in the study population

Acetabular Anteversion: Out of 52 cases, 46(88.4 %) patients had an acetabular anteversion between 5-25 degrees, 4 patients (7.7%) had an anteversion above 25 degrees and 2 patient (3.84%) had an anteversion below 5 degrees.

Figure 20: Acetabular anteversion observed in the study population

Femoral Stem Alignment: Out of 52 cases, 29(55.7%) had a neutral stem alignment while 16 (30.7%) had a varus alignment and 7 (13.46%) had valgus alignment.

Figure 21: Femoral Stem Alignment observed in the study population

Femoral Offset

Vertical Offset: Out of 52 cases, 7(13.46 %) patients had a vertical offset between 4.51-5.9 cm, 45 patients (86.5%) had a vertical offset above 5.95 cm and none had a vertical offset below 4.5 cm

Figure 22: Vertical offset observed in the study population

Ratio of vertical offset of the operated hip and the normal hip was also calculated. Out of 52 cases, 32(61.5%) were found to be with the range of 0.8-1.2. Other 20 cases (38.5%) had a ratio above 1.2 while none of the patient had it below 0.8.

Figure 23: Vertical offset ratio observed in the study population

Horizontal Offset: Out of 52 cases, 39 (75 %) patients had a horizontal offset between 3.4-4.8 cm, 3 cases (5.7%) had a horizontal offset above 4.8 cm and 10 (19.2%) cases had a horizontal offset below 3.4.

Figure 24: Horizontal offset observed in the study population

Ratio of horizontal offset of the operated hip and the normal hip was also calculated. Out of 52 cases, 36(69.2%) were found to be with the range of 0.8-1.2. Other 13 cases (25%) had a ratio above 1.2 while 3 patients (5.7%) had it below 0.8.

Figure 25: Horizontal offset ratio observed in the study population

Leg Length Discrepancy (LLD): Out of 52 cases, 50 (96.2 %) patients had a LLD within acceptable range (-10 mm to +10 mm), 2 (3.8%) patients had a lengthening of more than 10 mm while none had a shortening more than 10 mm.

Figure 26: Limb Length Discrepancy observed in the study population

Table 2: Measurement of variables in the study population

Variables	Normal	range	N (%)
Acetabular inclination	(Wylde et al 2012) 45 + 10°	< 35°	1(1.9)
		35-55°	48(92.3)
		>55°	3(5.7)
Acetabular anteversion	(Vanrusselt / et al 2015) 15 + 10°	<50	2 (3.84)
		5-25°	46(88.46)
		>25°	4(7.69)
Femoral Stem Alignment	(Haversath et al. 2019) Varus (2+1°) Neutral (<+1°/ - 1°) Valgus(s) - 1°	Varus	16 (30.7)
		Neutral	29(55.7)
		Valgus	7(13.46)
Vertical offset	(Rawal et al) Mean+SD 5.233.0.719 cm	(<4.51cm)	0
		(4.51-5.95cm)	7(13.46)
		(>5.95 cm)	45(86.5)
Vertical offset ratio(Operated side/Normal)	Normal(0.8-1.2) (Range taken in our study)	< 0.8 0.8-1.2	0 32(61.5)

		> 1.2	20(38.5%)
Horizontal Offset	(Husman et al) 4.05+0.75 cm	(<3.4cm) (3.4-4.8cm) (>4.8cm)	10(19.2) 39(75) 3(5.7)
Horizontal offset ratio(Operated side/Normal)	Normal(0.8-1.2) (Range taken in our study)	<0.8 0.8-1.2 > 1.2	3(5.7) 36(69.2) 13(25)
Leg Length Discrepancy	(Mahmood et al 2015) < 10 mm of shortening or lengthening	>10 mm of shortening Within Normal Range >10 mm of lengthening	0 50 (96.2) 2 (3.8)

Discussion

Understanding the biomechanics of injuries, designing implants for various surgeries, and understanding joint related pathologies such as arthritis all require knowledge of the proximal femur and acetabular geometry. The findings of this study may aid surgeons in restoring the natural biomechanics of the native hip joint during hip surgery.

Horizontal and vertical offsets: In his study, Rawal et al [21] found the mean vertical offset to be 5.233 +/- 0.7 cm. In our study, most of the patients had a vertical offset over 5.95 cm. Increased vertical offset was attempted to regain the limb length. It can also be attributed to the lateral positioning of the patient used in posterolateral approach with lower limb in adduction. [22] In his study, Husman et al [23] found horizontal offset to be 4.05 +/- 0.75 cm.

In our study, most of the patients had a horizontal offset within the range of 3.4-4.8 cm. 19.2% of the patients had a horizontal offset below 3.4 cm while only 5.7% patients had a horizontal offset over 4.8 cm. In our study, most of the patients (61.5%) had a vertical offset ratio within the normal range while 38.5% of the patients had a ratio more than 1.2. None of the patients had a ratio less than 0.8. While measuring the horizontal offset ratio, we found most of the patients to have a ratio within normal range (69.2%) while one fourth of the patient had a ratio more than 1.2 and 5.7% had a ratio below 0.8.

Acetabular Inclination: Wylde et al 2012 [24] in his study found the mean acetabular inclination to be 45 +/- 10 degrees. In our study, maximum number of patients (92.3%) had an acetabular inclination within the normal range. 5.7% of the patients had an inclination over 55 degrees while 1.9% had an inclination less than 35 degrees.

Acetabular Anteversion: In his study, Vanrusselt J et al 2015 [24] found the normal range of acetabular anteversion to be 15 +/- 10 degrees. In our study, most of the cases (88.46%) had an acetabular anteversion in the normal range. 7.69% of the patients had an acetabular anteversion above 25 degrees while 3.4% of the patients had it below 5 degrees.

Femoral Stem Alignment: Haversath et al. 2019 [25] in his study had defined the stem alignment to be in neutral position if the angle made between the longitudinal axis of femur and tip of the stem is within -1 to +1 degrees. Any deviation from the same has to be considered as valgus or varus alignment. In our study, we found that 55.7% of patients had a neutral alignment while 30.7% of the patients had a varus alignment and 13.46% of patients had a valgus alignment of the femoral stem.

Leg Length Discrepancy: Mahmood et al 2015 [26] in their studies had found the acceptable range of leg length discrepancy to be not more 10 mm of shortening or lengthening. In our study, Most of the patients (96.2%) had a leg length discrepancy of less than 10 mm while 3.8% of patients had gained more 10 mm of limb length. None of the patients had a shortening of more than 10 mm in our study.

Conclusion

In our study, we radiologically analysed the acetabular cup and femoral stem orientation in uncemented total hip arthroplasty performed via the posterolateral approach. We observed that the radiological outcome of both acetabular and femoral component orientation is in line with the findings of the studies done previously in similar setups. The only variable noted was in the vertical offset of the femoral component which was slightly higher than the previously set standardised range in other studies.

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